

ISic1319

I.Sicily inscription 1319

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania (?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140812

1. Θ (εοῖς) Κ (αταχθονίοις) .
2. Π[ρ]ειμι-
3. τεῖβε χρη[σ]-
4. τὲ χαῖρε. ἔ-
5. ζησες ἔτη
6. θ'.
- 7.
8. Θ (εοῖς) □ Κ (αταχθονίοις) .
9. Κου[ε]ίντα, [έ]-
10. βίωσεν ἔτη
11. ιδ. Κοπρία
12. μήτηρ ἐ[πο]ί-
13. ησεν.
- 14.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492924

EDCS 39101689

PHI 140812

Bibliography

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Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0497 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum.* Berlin. At 3.5722

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